

ISic1194

I.Sicily inscription 1194

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, San Marco d'Alunzio

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140678

1. [οἱ ἄλ]ειφόμεν[ο]ι Φίντων [α]
2. [— — — —] Εὐμ[α]χον. {²⁷Εὐμ[ηλ]ον}²⁷
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492799

EDCS 39101558

PHI 140678

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1194. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385578>